

Evaluating Patient Satisfaction with Services at the Pharmacy of the National Hospital of Obstetrics and Gynecology in 2024

Nong Manh Tu ✉, Nguyen Huy Tuan, Le Thi Ngoc Huong
Nguyen Thi Nhung, Nguyen Van Cong

Host Organization: National Hospital of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Vietnam

Abstract

The study aims to evaluate and identify factors associated with patient satisfaction with the pharmacy services at the National Hospital of Obstetrics and Gynecology in 2024. A total of 425 interview responses were collected using a questionnaire. Patients reported a high level of satisfaction, with an average satisfaction score of 9.13 (SD = 0.81). Notably, 98.8% of patients rated their satisfaction at 8 or higher. The highest proportion of patients, 39.1%, gave a rating of 9/10. Exploratory factor analysis revealed three extracted factor groups. Multivariate linear regression analysis identified two statistically significant factors influencing satisfaction: the outcomes of services provided at the pharmacy ($p = 0.002$) and accessibility and transparency of administrative procedures ($p < 0.001$). These two factors accounted for 25.9% of the variation in satisfaction levels. Patients expressed high satisfaction with the pharmacy services at the National Hospital of Obstetrics and Gynecology. The identified factors influencing satisfaction include the outcomes of services provided at the pharmacy and the accessibility and transparency of administrative procedures.

Introduction

The satisfaction index is an important measure in evaluating the service of agencies in general and civil servants in particular to the people [1]. The Ministry of Health has issued a project "Determining methods to measure people's satisfaction with public health services" and an implementation plan "Innovating the service style and attitude of medical staff towards patient satisfaction". To maintain and improve hospital quality, the Department of Medical Examination and Treatment Management - Ministry of Health organizes teams to assess hospital quality and conduct surveys on satisfaction criteria of patients and medical staff for hospital operations [2]. However, the hospital quality assessment checklist issued by the Ministry of Health currently only evaluates overall activities in the hospital. For each hospital with gradual financial autonomy, patient satisfaction is an important factor in measuring the quality of health care, improving treatment efficiency and increasing reputation of the hospital, creating competitiveness with other hospitals; ensure economic operations and development [3].

National Hospital of Obstetrics and Gynecology is a leading facility specializing in obstetrics and newborns. Currently, the Faculty of Pharmacy organizes a pharmacy system including 02 pharmacies for 2 large medical examination areas of the hospital. Improving treatment efficiency and service quality of the hospital to meet patient satisfaction is an urgent and consistent task in the direction of the Board of Directors for each department in the hospital [4]. However, evaluating the performance of each pharmacy is usually done in the form of comparing monthly sales, monitoring patient feedback, etc., but there is no scientific way to evaluate specifically about the operational quality of each pharmacy. Therefore, we proceed to implement the topic [5].

Research Objects and Methods

The cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted during the period from June 2024 to December 2024. 425 observations were included in the analysis. Inclusion criteria include: the patient agrees to participate in the study; 18 years old or older; Have normal mental health and be able to communicate and

More Information

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answer questions. Exclusion criteria include: patients who do not directly buy drugs at the pharmacy system of the National Hospital of Obstetrics and Gynecology, patients who return to buy old prescriptions, or patients who buy drugs freely at the pharmacy. Research variables exploited through direct interviews include variables describing the patient's personal characteristics; variable assessing access to hospital pharmacy; variables describing information transparency and administrative procedures at the hospital pharmacy; Descriptive variable about hospital pharmacy facilities; Descriptive variable for hospital pharmacy sales staff; variable describing the outcome

of services performed at the hospital pharmacy; and the output variable evaluates the level of satisfaction. Analyze data using SPSS 25 statistical software. Apply descriptive analysis methods to provide information about patient characteristics: calculate frequency, percentage, average value, standard deviation. EFA exploratory factor analysis and multivariate linear regression analysis to identify factors affecting patient satisfaction.

Research Results

425 observations collected between June 2024 and December 2023 yield the following results:

General characteristics

Table 1. General Characteristics of Study Subjects

No	Characteristic	Value
1	Age	34.75 (SD = 9.18)
2	Ethnic (n=421) Kinh ethnicity Other ethnicities	417 (99.0%) 4 (1.0%)
3	Profession (n=425) Civil servant/officer Worker Farmer Free business Retired Other	76 (17.9%) 122 (28.7%) 45 (10.6%) 101 (23.8%) 3 (0.7%) 78 (18.4%)
4	Average monthly income (million VND)	8.52 (SD = 4.88)
5	Education level (n=425) Below high school High school Intermediate/College level University/Post-graduate	32 (7.5%) 131 (30.8%) 136 (32%) 126 (29.6%)
6	Current residence (n=425) Hanoi inner city Outside Hanoi Other provinces	105 (24.7%) 60 (14.1%) 260 (61.2%)
7	Hospital visits (n=425) First time Second time More than twice	88 (20.7%) 148 (34.8%) 189 (44.5%)

Source: Author's own compilation

The results of general characteristics showed that the average age of patients participating in the study was about 34.75 years old with an average monthly income of 8.52 million VND. Most of the patients participating in the study were of Kinh ethnicity (accounting for 99% of the survey questionnaires collected). The proportion of patients with education levels at the High School, Intermediate/College and University/Post-graduate levels is not too different. 61.2% of patients living in provinces other than Hanoi came for medical examination and buying medicine. The majority of participating patients visited the hospital more than twice, accounting for 44.5%.

Factors affecting patient satisfaction

Patients are satisfied with the quality of service at the pharmacy system of the National Obstetrics Hospital with an average rating of 9.13 points (SD= 0.81). The proportion of patients who rated the score 9/10 was the highest at 39.1%, with 98.8% of patients interviewed saying they were satisfied with a score of 8 or higher.

Based on the results of the third factor rotation matrix, it can be seen that 4 groups of factors were extracted and explained 62.145% of the variation in the data. The newly renamed factor groups include the results of services performed at the pharmacy, facilities and

pharmacy staff, and accessibility and transparency of administrative procedures.

Table 2. Factors Affecting Patient Satisfaction

No	Element	B coefficient	Beta coefficient	p	VIF
	Constant	5.144			
1	NT1	0.366	0.184	0.002	1.920
2	NT3	0.561	0.364	<0.001	1.920
R ² = 0.259					
R ² correction = 0.256					

Source: Author's own compilation

Factors 2, facilities and pharmacy staff, were removed in linear regression analysis because their influence on satisfaction was not statistically significant. There are 2 factors that affect patient satisfaction with statistical significance NT1. Results of services performed at the pharmacy with p = 0.002 and NT3. Accessibility and transparency of administrative procedures with p<0.001. The beta coefficients for the two factors are both positive, so this group of factors affects satisfaction in the same direction.

Conclusion

Research results show that patient satisfaction with drug sales and service activities at the National Hospital of Obstetrics and Gynecology pharmacy system is at a good level, with an average score of 9.13 (SD= 0.81) on the scale score 10, with 98.8% of interviewed patients saying they were satisfied with a score of 8 or higher. Compare with some other studies around the world. In Ethiopia, the score assessing patient satisfaction with services at the hospital pharmacy is 2.70/5 (SD= 0.83), in Thailand it is 5.27/7 (SD= 0.94).). Compared with private pharmacies in the community, patient satisfaction with the services of some pharmacies in Hanoi city is at 4.31/5 (SD= 0.55) and has 95.5 % of patients rated as satisfied or very satisfied (4 points or more).

Although there are many different characteristics of hospital pharmacies compared to community pharmacies, such as a larger number of patients and pharmacists and drug sellers who have less opportunity to advise patients, it can be seen that the ratio The patient satisfaction rate is still relatively high, higher or nearly equivalent to that of private pharmacies.

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